

**A CORRELATIONAL STUDY BETWEEN MACHISMO AND ATTITUDE
TOWARD SEEKING PROFESSIONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL HELP
OF SELECTED EARLY MALE ADULTS**

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A Correlational Study Between Machismo and Attitude toward Seeking Professional Psychological Help of Selected Early Male Adults

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Abstract

Machismo culture is the expected view of society towards men, such as a man should always be the family provider and independent. However, because of the gender roles, the importance of mental help-seeking remained left behind due to prejudices resulting in men's negative attitudes towards seeking mental help. Researchers investigate the association between the level of machismo and attitude towards seeking professional psychological help. The present study examined the Early adult males ages 20-40 years old, residing within Metro Manila or Cavite (n=100). Collected the data according to demographics such as civil status, employment status, and nature of employment. Mixed-method design was used, and structured interviews through online and survey questionnaires were used to collect data. Results revealed that there is a strong correlation between the level of machismo and attitude towards seeking professional psychological help, as the computed value of Pearson's $r = 0.70$. Based on the t-test (9.70) is greater than the critical value of 1.987, indicating that the correlation is statistically significant, indicating that the increase in level of machismo will also increase the negative attitude towards seeking mental help. Findings suggest mental health interventions could contribute to understanding of gender roles and to support men to increase help seeking behavior.

Keywords: *machismo, attitude, psychological help-seeking, early male adults*

Introduction

Traditionally, men are raised to be strong and independent and to never display any type of vulnerability. This type of culture is still prevalent to this day. A lot of men consider seeking professional help for their psychological problems to be a form of weakness because they believe that, as men, they should be independent and should be able to handle all their problems on their own. Men also fear the stigma associated with getting treatment for their mental problems as they fear that other people might label them as "crazy" or as insane person if they do seek treatment. Researchers believe that men should be able to seek treatment for their mental health problems without the fear of stigma from other people and without them feeling that they are compromising their masculinity because of it.

According to Quintana (2021) and Sotelo (2022), machismo originates from Latin American and Spanish culture, where it is a social-behavioral concept that lays out the ideal societal role that men are expected to play in their communities. Through machismo, men are expected to embody traditional masculine characteristics such as independence, strength, aggression, anger, courage, power, and dominance and to never display any form of weakness or vulnerability with a focus directed more toward the negative aspects of masculinity. In the Philippines, the same characteristics that are associated with machismo are also prevalent and are imposed on the men of the country. The present study, titled "A Correlational Study Between Machismo and Attitude Towards Seeking Professional Psychological Help of Selected Early Male Adults," aims to assess the relationship between the independent and dependent variables mentioned. As to the purpose of this study, the researchers would like to understand and further examine if the perceived level of machismo hinders men from seeking professional mental help.

As to a previous study, the number of Filipinos who are willing to seek out help and have sought out help from mental health professionals for their psychological problems is already few. The number of Filipino men seeking help is even fewer compared to the Filipino women who have sought out help. This is because Filipino men were raised to embody the traditional masculine characteristics associated with the machismo present in the Philippines. According to Panaligan (2021), many Filipino men find it difficult to express such emotions and behaviors due to the fact that they were raised to keep their emotions to themselves because of the thought that they don't want to burden other people by talking about their personal problems. Also, some of them have stated that their family and friends told them they, being the men that they are, should just brush off any negative emotion that they feel. This results in frequent struggles to put their emotions into words and/or are told to just pray their mental problems away.

The prevailing walls of lower prevalence of help-seeking and negative attitudes of men are the gender role in society that commonly drives men to be strong, independent, competitive, and invulnerable. Gender is the construct of norms, shaping the behaviors and beliefs and the expectations for every gender to adhere to the appropriate activities and attributes. Because of these ideologies, men who experience psychological distress perceive that same distress as a threat and assume any engagement in psychological treatment to be considered a weakness, something to be associated with femininity, and are vulnerable to inferiority. Nonetheless, the fact that stigma against mental illness is pervasive in the Philippines, regardless of gender, Filipino men's attitudes toward mental illness are frequently influenced by both hegemonic masculine norms and everyday Filipino customs. In the Philippines, the phrase "Kalalakimongtao" is commonly thrown around, usually accompanied by words like "malambot", "iyakin", and "takot". Some Filipino men have stated that those phrases made them build up walls to conceal their feelings growing up. Because of this, a lot of men never

learned the proper way to interpret their emotions. Also, since most Filipino men were raised to adhere to the same hegemonic masculinity, a lot of men find it difficult to find other male friends who they are able to express their emotions with. When they do open up to each other, they tend to downplay their emotions or not speak about them seriously.

Hence, this may result in them developing codependent relationships with female partners or adopting unhealthy coping mechanisms like substance abuse. A lot of Filipino men tend to view vulnerability as a weakness while associating aggression with strength. In the Filipino culture, the only emotions that men are allowed to have are positive ones, while they are taught to ignore negative emotions except for anger, which is the only negative emotion that is seen as “manly”. Some Filipino men who don’t conform to traditional masculine values are called with homophobic slurs. The slurs were used to shame men whenever they displayed cowardice. All these reasons are possibly hindering Filipino men from seeking professional help. Men feel like it’s weak and unmanly to go to therapy, and they fear that they are going to be ridiculed if they seek or receive formal help from other professionals. Seeking professional help is not aligned with the values expected particularly of men by the norms of society, and that is why men prefer to instead bottle up all of their problems. This bottling up of problems is also one of the biggest reasons that push men to act impulsively and engage themselves in a horrible lifetime mistakes such as committing suicide. The rate of male suicide is two to four times higher compared to women (Simon et al. 2021). In addition, men who possess problems that they are unable to find a solution to or manage are put in a state of despair when they are also unable to ask for help from other people for fear of ridicule which leads them to commit suicide.

Considering the high rates of the male population that have experienced emotional crises, formal mental help-seeking is still an unacceptable last resort for solving and getting rid of their emotional conflicts. Formal mental help services are the services offered by professionally trained personnel who are typically compensated for their work, such as a psychiatrist and psychologist who assists with mental health disorders, as well as facilities, such as mental health institutions. According to Wendt et al. (2016), men are consequently much less likely than women to visit doctors, communicate with healthcare providers, and participate in particular formal help-seeking programs since men are often trained into a masculine gender role, imposed on males to uphold a socially established masculine ideal that emphasizes independence, emotional restraint, self-reliance, and the rejection of a vulnerable personal life. These expectations seem to have an even bigger effect on men who seek out formal assistance. Men who want or need professional help may encounter major obstacles because of their personal and social perceptions of formal help-seeking, which are often held negatively amongst men. This may play a role in explaining the gender disparity in formal help-seeking, especially in light of the fact that a recent study found that males are more likely than women to view mental health treatment with stigma. In addition, males frequently worry that their peers, relatives, and acquaintances will turn away from them or treat them less masculinely if they seek, need, or visit a mental medical professional. These challenges highlight the necessity for clinicians and academics to stop adversely impacting and unfavorable stereotypes about men, especially those men who are willing to seek out mental health professionals. The researchers use these underlying issues to gauge the respondents’ level of machismo and attitudes toward seeking psychological help. This research aims to provide subsequent knowledge about the machismo culture that prevents early male adults from seeking psychological help.

According to previous studies, there are still underlying problems, gaps, and insufficient knowledge when it comes to an understanding of the practice of psychology in the Philippines, especially in layman’s understanding. Some Filipinos are still close-minded to the topic of mental health because of their religious view, the permanence of social stigma in our society, and the prejudices. Therefore, people with mental health problems hesitate to seek professional help. Researchers would like to enlighten society on the importance of formal psychological help, as well as adult males’ mental health is particularly relevant just as women do. Furthermore, the study would like to stand along with people suffering from emotional crises and stop discrimination surrounding help-seeking. Men should have the freedom to express their emotions and seek professional help without the fear of negative judgment from other people. Men shouldn’t have to feel like seeking help is an attack on their masculinity, and instead, acts like seeking help, opening up to other people, and expressing emotions should be incorporated to masculinity.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents when they are grouped according to:
 - 1.1. Civil Status
 - 1.2. Employment Status
 - 1.3. Nature of Employment
2. What is the level of machismo when respondents are grouped according to demographic profile?
3. What is the level of attitudes toward seeking professional psychological help of respondents when they were grouped according to demographic profile?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of machismo when they are grouped according to demographic profile?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of attitudes on seeking professional psychological help when they are grouped according to demographic profile?
6. Is there a significant correlation between machismo and attitude toward seeking professional psychological help?
7. What intervention can be proposed out of the conduct of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers aim to assess the relationship between machismo and the attitudes of early adult males toward seeking professional psychological help. Therefore, this study utilizes a mixed method design, the quantitative, where systematically investigates an observable phenomenon to explain, predict, and identify a pattern in a sensation approach that is practical for examining the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. And qualitative to examine and also support the quantitative results. Furthermore, both analysis is used to determine whether the two variables are correlated. The researchers utilize a correlational design that assesses the relationship between two or more variables without controlling for extraneous variables, as it paints a clearer picture of the study.

The researchers used the mixed method design that combines two elements of a method that strengthens and expands the study's conclusion, contributing to published literature (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017). A sequential explanatory was used as the best fit to answer the question and draw a broader conclusion commencing, and it has two phases: a quantitative followed by a qualitative. During the process, the data was collected and analyzed separately. In the qualitative phase, the findings are used to explain and contextualize the quantitative findings.

Respondents

This study gathered 100 respondents that met the following criteria:

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of Respondents*

Profile	Frequency (N=100)	Percent
Civil Status		
Single	93	93%
Married	6	6%
Separated	1	1%
Employment Status		
Employed	43	43%
Unemployed	47	47%
Self-employed	10	10%
Nature of Employment		
Private Sector	39	39%
Public Sector	7	7%
NA	54	54%

The study by Nuñez, Alicia, et al. (2016) addresses that the early adult's respondent variable, such as civil status, is correlated with their gender attitudes, which relates to the present study, the findings of which discussed the changes of gender norms toward masculinity in the context of marriage. The study shows that through broadening the different gender cultures across cultures, the study includes that the male breadwinner norm is lower than the previous societal expectation towards men. To summarize, the norm that a man should be the provider of the family in modern years is unexpectedly low to the usual view of society towards men, which indicates almost no effect on the level of machismo according to civil status.

The participants included in the study are early adult males residing in Metro Manila or Cavite. In this study, the researchers used non-probability sampling in which the target sample size is based on the researcher's subjective judgment and non-random selection of samples. In order to select participants, the study used purposive sampling in which respondents are selected based on criteria set by the researchers for the particular group of interest. This method is commonly chosen when a particular characteristic, feature, or area of interest of the research subject, such as a group of individuals who share common characteristics such as age, gender, background, etc. This sampling is typical in survey research and practice used to investigate specific research areas of interest (Vijayamohan 2022). The researchers then selected a total of 100 early male adults for the survey questionnaire and 10 males from 100 respondents who answered the survey questionnaire for a structured interview.

Instrument

The researchers used two instruments for gathering subsequent data for the study. Google Forms was the chosen platform to easily collect the responses from the respondents. Self-made survey questionnaire and interview guide are the instruments that are used to measure the key variables of the study and answer the following statement of the problem. For quantitative data, the survey questionnaire consists of two parts: 20 statements for the level of machismo with a value for the Cronbach's alpha for the instrument

was $\alpha = .725$, which indicates an acceptable internal consistency of the instrument, and 20 statements for attitude towards seeking professional psychological help with a value for the Cronbach's alpha for the instrument was $\alpha = .886$, which indicates good internal consistency of the instrument. The 4-point Likert scale was used to indicate the degree of agreement per statement: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. The 4-point Likert scale was the ideal type of scale to collect feedback with extreme feedback and straight to the point degree of agreement towards the statement provided. For qualitative, interview questions were provided therein to collect substantial qualitative opinions from the respondents. It consists of five structured open-ended questions. The research team used an instrument with a set of statements aligned with the research objectives. The purpose of the survey questionnaire and interview questions is to provide and gather significant data that would help the researchers to analyze the hypotheses and research questions. The research team will ensure that the responses are anonymous to avoid biases and data confidentiality.

The survey questionnaire is composed of statements that helped the researchers to know if there is a significance between the machismo and attitudes of early male adults towards help-seeking. As the majority of responses from the level of machismo yield to agree as the degree of the agreement indicates a moderate level of machismo, and the majority of responses from the attitude towards seeking professional psychological help-seeking yield to agree, indicating a negative attitude towards mental help.

The interview questions are to provide qualitative support for the data gathered in the quantitative survey questionnaire. It consists of five open-ended structured questions related to the relationship between machismo culture and attitudes toward seeking professional psychological help.

Procedure

To gather data for this study, a survey was conducted among a total of 100 male respondents between the ages of 20 and 40 who are residing in Metro Manila or Cavite. Given the current pandemic situation, the research team took all necessary precautions and followed the health protocols and guidelines to ensure the safety of both the researchers and the respondents. To administer the survey questionnaire, the researchers utilized Google Forms that were validated by a psychometrician and the students of the BPSY - 4A class. This platform allowed the researchers to easily distribute the survey questionnaire and efficiently collect the significant data needed to achieve the study objectives. The researchers carefully selected appropriate respondents for the survey and requested proper permission and consent to participate in the research. The researchers made sure to emphasize to every respondent the importance of their cooperation to the success of the research. The five researchers were assigned to gather 20 respondents, each with a total of 100 to answer the survey. From 100 respondents, 10 were selected to answer the interview questions. The respondents were informed that their responses would be secured and kept confidential even after the research.

Data Analysis

This study used a mixed-method approach that combined both quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative data were analyzed using several statistical treatments, which were chosen based on their ability to address the research questions and hypotheses. These treatments included calculating Mean, one-way ANOVA, Pearson's correlation coefficient, T-test, and determining the critical value. Additionally, the study gathered qualitative data through interviews with 10 early male adults to explore their perception on machismo and attitudes towards machismo towards seeking professional psychological help. The qualitative data was analyzed thematically to identify common themes and patterns related to the research questions. The following is a description of each statistical treatment used and how it was applied to the study:

Mean

The mean was used to calculate the average scores for machismo and attitudes toward seeking professional psychological help among early male adults. This statistical treatment was used to compare the levels of machismo and attitudes toward seeking help among different demographic groups, including civil status, employment status, and nature of employment. By examining the mean scores for each group, the researchers were able to identify any significant differences or patterns in machismo and help-seeking attitudes.

One-way ANOVA

One-way ANOVA was used to determine whether there were significant differences in the mean scores of machismo and attitudes toward seeking professional psychological help across different demographic groups. Specifically, it was used to compare the mean scores of the selected early male adults across different levels of demographic variables such as civil status, employment status, and nature of employment. This statistical treatment was chosen to test the null hypothesis that there were no significant differences between the means of different groups.

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient

Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between machismo and attitudes toward seeking professional psychological help. This statistical treatment helped to determine whether there was a significant positive or negative correlation between the two variables. A positive correlation would indicate that higher levels of machismo were associated with a more negative attitude toward seeking help, while a negative correlation would indicate the opposite.

Hypothesis Test

A T-test was used to determine whether there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the two groups. Specifically, a T-test was used to compare the mean scores of early male adults who reported high levels of machismo to those who reported low levels of machismo. This statistical treatment was chosen to test the null hypothesis that there were no significant differences in the mean scores between the two groups.

Critical Value

The critical value was used to determine whether the computed T-test was statistically significant by comparing the computed t-test value to the critical value. If the computed t-test value was greater than the critical value, reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the two groups of early male adults in terms of their machismo culture and attitudes towards seeking professional psychological help.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data analysis, interpretation, and discussion of the results gathered from the respondents who are early adult males living within Metro Manila or Cavite. The raw data were supported by the statistical analysis presented through tables following the sequence of the problem statement regarding the correlation between machismo and attitude toward seeking professional psychological help of selected early male adults.

SOP 1: What is the demographic profile of respondents when they are grouped according to: Civil Status, Employment Status and Nature of employment

Based on the table 1 shown above, the average respondents in the civil status category per demographic profile are classified as single, married, and separated. There are 93% of Single respondents, 6% of Married respondents, and 1% of separated respondents. To sum it up, Single status covers the highest portion of respondents civil status, while separated have the lowest count of respondents. the average respondents' employment status per demographic profile is classified as Employed, Unemployed, and Self-employed. Also, there are 47% of unemployed respondents, 43% of employed respondents, and 10% of Self-employed respondents. In totality, unemployed respondents cover the highest portion of employment status, while self-employed have the lowest count of respondents. Results shown are the average Nature of employment by early adults per demographic profile. 38% of respondents who are working in the private sector, which includes firms, clinics, and business establishments or stores for the self-employed. While there are 8% of respondents who are working in the public sector, which includes teachers, professors, lawyers, police, and barangay officials, and to unemployed and respondents who cannot identify their nature of employment. For example, pedicab and tricycle drivers who participated in the study, respondents, there are 54% of respondents who are not working either in the public or private sector.

SOP 2: What is the level of machismo when respondents were grouped according to demographic profile?

Table 2. *Level of Machismo per Demographic Profile of Respondents*

<i>Civil Status</i>		
Single	2.6	Married 2.67
		Separated 2.8
<i>Employment Status</i>		
Employed	2.65	Self-Employed 2.53
		Unemployed 2.7
<i>Nature of Employment</i>		
Private Sector	2.58	Public Sector 2.94
		NA 2.57

Based on the result shown in Table 2, the mean level of machismo per demographic profile of respondents is: in terms of civil status: Single 2.60, Married 2.67, and separated 2.80. In terms of employment status: Employed 2.65, Unemployed 2.53, and Self-employed 2.74. In terms of nature of employment: Private sector 2.58, Public Sector 2.94, and Unemployed respondents (N/A) 2.57. Which respectively are equivalent to "agree" as the degree of agreement. With the result stated, the respondents agree with the existence and expected qualities of machismo formed by the society- traditionally and culturally based on the provided statement from part 1 of the survey, which measures the level of machismo of the respondent.

SOP 3: What is the level of attitudes on seeking professional psychological help of respondents when they were grouped according to demographic profile?

Based on the result shown in Table 3, the mean level of attitude towards seeking professional psychological help per demographic profile of respondents is: in terms of civil status: Single with 2.50, Married with 1.98, and separated with 2.25. Which respectively indicates that single respondents are likely to show an agreeable attitude to the negative perception towards mental help-seeking and are less likely to seek professional psychological help.

Table 3. *Attitude towards Seeking Professional Psychological Help per Demographic Profile of the respondents*

<i>Civil Status</i>		
Single	2.5	Married 1.98
		Separated 2.25
<i>Employment Status</i>		
Employed	2.44	Self-Employed 2.44
		Unemployed 2.7
<i>Nature of Employment</i>		
Private Sector	2.45	Public Sector 2.62
		NA 2.46

While married and separated respondents disagree, which expresses that they are more likely open to seeking professional psychological help. Similarly, in terms of employment status: Employed with 2.44, Unemployed with 2.44, and Self-employed with 2.70. This explains that employed and unemployed respondents are more likely to seek professional psychological help. In comparison, self-employed have an agreeable attitude to the negative perception of mental help-seeking and are less likely to seek professional psychological help. In terms of nature of employment: The private sector with 2.45, Public Sector with 2.64, and Unemployed respondents (N/A) with 2.46. The public sector, including teachers, professors, lawyers, and government officials, are less likely to seek psychological help and agreeable negative attitudes towards seeking professional psychological help. While the private sector, which includes employees from firms and business owners, is more open to seeking psychological help and entails disagreement to negative attitudes towards seeking professional psychological help.

SOP 4: Is there a significant difference in the level of machismo when they are grouped according to demographic profile?

Table 4. *Test of Difference in the Level of Machismo when Grouped according to Civil Status*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.418103333	2	0.209052	0.558636865	0.575087905	3.158842719
Within Groups	21.330395	57	0.374217			
Total	21.74849833	59				

Failed to reject null Hypothesis

Using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), it was possible to examine the level of machismo among groups of people based on their civil status (single, married, and separated). The findings of a one-way ANOVA show that there is insufficient data to reject the null hypothesis because there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the three groups ($F(2,57) = 0.55, p > 0.05, n_2 = .19$).

Table 5. *Test of Difference in the Level of Machismo when Grouped according to Employment Status*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.443103333	2	0.221552	0.949327627	0.39303396	3.158842719
Within Groups	13.302515	57	0.233377			
Total	13.74561833	59				

Failed to reject null Hypothesis

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to examine the differences in the level of machismo when grouped according to the status of employment (employed, unemployed, and self-employed). A one-way ANOVA result indicates that there were no significant differences among the mean scores of the three groups ($F(2,57) = 0.94, p > .05, n_2 = .32$, which entails insufficient evidence to not reject the null hypothesis).

Table 6. *Test of Difference in the Level of Machismo when Grouped according to Nature of Employment*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	1.75773	2	0.878865	2.914810604	0.06233713	3.158842719
Within Groups	17.18647	57	0.301517			
Total	18.9442	59				

Failed to reject null Hypothesis

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to examine the differences in the level of machismo when grouped according to the nature of employment (public sector, private sector, and N/A) among a sample of 100 early male adults. The ANOVA did not yield a significant difference in the level of machismo between the groups, $F(2, 57) = 2.91, p > 0.05, \eta^2 = .093$, indicating that there is no

significant difference in the level of machismo when grouped according to nature of employment.

The decision for H01, providing the analysis of data, shows that there is no significant difference in the level of machismo when grouped according to demographic profile, indicating failure to reject the null hypothesis (H01). Analysis revealed that civil status, employment status, and nature of employment yield corresponding statistics of p-value greater than the alpha level.

SOP 5: Is there a significant difference in the level of attitudes on seeking professional psychological help when they are grouped according to demographic profile?

Table 7. *Test of Difference in the level of attitudes toward seeking professional psychological help when grouped according to Civil Status*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	2.67897	2	1.339485	6.157153669	0.003792985	3.158842719
Within Groups	12.400315	57	0.217549			
Total	15.079285	59				

Reject the Null Hypothesis

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to compare the levels of attitudes toward professional psychological help according to civil status. A one-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference between the three groups ($F(2,57) = 6.157$, $p < 0.05$, $n_2 = 0.178$). A Tukey-Kramer post hoc test for multiple comparisons found that the mean scores between the single and separated groups, as well as between the married and separated groups, had no statistically significant differences between them, while it was found that there is a statistically significant difference between the single and married groups as the gap between their mean scores was large enough to be considered significant.

Table 8. *Test of Difference in the Level of Attitudes toward Seeking Professional Psychological Help when grouped according to Employment Status*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.891213333	2	0.445607	5.246698037	0.008100035	3.158842719
Within Groups	4.84106	57	0.084931			
Total	5.732273333	59				

Reject the Null Hypothesis

A one-way analysis (ANOVA) was performed to compare the level of mean scores when grouped to employment status wherein the Employed ($n = 43$), Unemployed ($n = 47$), and Self-employed ($n = 10$). It revealed that there was a statistically significant difference according to employment status ($F(2,27) = 5.246$, $p < 0.05$, $n_2 = 0.155$). Post-hoc tests using the Tukey-Kramer test revealed that the mean scores between the employed and unemployed groups had no statistically significant difference between them as their mean scores are equal to each other. In contrast, the mean scores between the unemployed and self-employed groups and between the employed and self-employed groups have statistically significant differences between them.

Table 9. *Test of Difference in the Level of Attitudes toward Seeking Professional Psychological Help when grouped according to Nature of Employment*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.379263333	2	0.189632	1.458895119	0.241042388	3.158842719
Within Groups	7.409035	57	0.129983			
Total	7.788298333	59				

Failed to reject null Hypothesis

As shown in the table above, there was no identified statistically significant difference when grouped according to the nature of employment since the p-value (0.24) is greater than the alpha value (0.05), as well as that the f statistic (1.46) is less than the f critical or tabular f value (3.16), and determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(2, 57) = 1.45$, $p > 0.05$) that entails insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The decision for H02, providing the analysis of data that shows that there is a significant difference in the level of attitudes toward seeking professional psychological help when grouped according to demographic profile, indicates to reject the null hypothesis (H02). Analysis revealed that civil status and employment status yield corresponding statistics of p-value less than the alpha level, and the nature of employment has a p-value greater than the alpha level. The result shows that there is a significant difference in the level of attitude on seeking professional psychological help when grouped according to demographic profile.

SOP 6: Is there a significant correlation between machismo and of attitude on seeking professional psychological help?

Pearson's correlation coefficient was computed to examine the relationship between machismo and attitude towards seeking professional psychological help ($n = 100$). According to the set interpretation of Schober et. al (2018), the results revealed a strong positive correlation between machismo and attitude, $r(98) = 0.7$. The computed value ($r=0.7$) suggests that as the level of machismo increases, negative attitudes towards seeking professional psychological help also tend to increase. The critical value is 1.987, by identifying the degrees of freedom (98) and alpha level (0.05). The computed value of test statistics ($= 9.70$) is greater than the critical

value of 1.987, indicating that the correlation is statistically significant.

Table 10. Test of Relationship between the Level of Machismo and Attitude towards Seeking Professional Psychological Help

Variable	Statistics	Computed Value	Hypothesis Test			Interpretation
			(T-test)	Critical Value	Decision	
Machismo vs attitude	Pearson r	0.7	9.7	1.987	Strong Positive correlation	Significant

The result from the computed Pearson’s r reveals that there is a significant relationship between the level of machismo and attitude towards seeking professional psychological help ($r= 0.70$, $t= 9.70$, critical value =1.987). Suggests that both variables move in the exact same direction, indicates that the increase of level of machismo, there is also an increase of negative attitude towards seeking mental help.

SOP 7: What intervention can be proposed out of the conduct of the study?

Based on the suggestions from the respondents and the proposed intervention of the researchers, the study recommends three interventions that can encourage men to seek professional psychological help. The first intervention is to create awareness campaigns that highlight the benefits of seeking help and aim to break down the societal expectations and stigma surrounding mental health issues. The "Man Up" campaign can be launched through different media channels to reach a broader audience. The second intervention is to establish accessible support systems that are open, convenient, and easily reachable to men who need professional psychological help. This intervention addresses the importance of having a support system that is easily accessible and available when needed. Finally, the study recommends using testimonials and peer support groups, and discussions to help men connect with others who have had similar experiences and share their thoughts and emotions in a safe and non-judgmental environment. Overall, these interventions can help create a more supportive and accepting environment for men to seek help for their mental health concerns. The qualitative phase of this study focused on identifying the expectations of society from an early-adult male and the perception of the respondents towards professional psychological help-seeking. The results presented below detail the processes by which early male adults perceive machismo culture. These qualitative results sought to answer the following questions:

Questions and Summary of Responses for Qualitative Data

Table 11. What characteristics or roles define you as a man according to society? Do you agree or disagree with that notion, and why?

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	“Men should be the head of the family, and that only men can work. I don’t agree. Women can do things men can.” (Transcript A Line 1-3)	Society's masculine ideologies only formed for standardization and ideal responsibility for men.
3	“Society tells us that men have certain characteristics that define them as men. Some of these include being powerful, being tough, and being the provider. I disagree with these characteristics because society has made these characteristics the norm, and they have become the barometer by which men are measured. As a man, I strive to be a loving and supportive partner to my partner, not just a provider and a tough guy. I am not defined by these traits; but instead, I define myself by my actions.” (Transcript C Line 1-3)	
2	“Man is a grown-up or adult male.” (Transcript B Line 1)	Imposed roles as a man to its family.
6	“A man must be responsible at all times with his actions and must also establish his family firmly as the father. I agree with this since this biblical, and I firmly believe that it is the truth.” (Transcript F Line 1-2)	
4	“Strong and disciplined. Yes, I agree since, as a man, you need to be strong and disciplined in order to protect the ones you love and be a better person.” (Transcript D Line 1)	Accepted the notion or expectation of being strong, independent and protector.
5	“Provider and protector. I agree man should protect and provide for his loved ones.” (Transcript E Line 1)	
7	“Provider, agree; I don’t like being a nuisance couch potato at home.” (Transcript G ;Line 1)	
10	“By my biographical gender, I agree since it is what I have since birth.” (Transcript J Line 1)	Genetics and sexuality are related to adherence of following machismo roles.
8	“You must always be strong and have the male genitalia.” (Transcript H Line 1)	
9	“Through my genitalia. I totally agree.” (Transcript I Line 1)	

Table 12. What or who was the primary reason that influenced your manliness? In what way did it influence you? Explain thoroughly

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	“Family. Society. Environment. My family plays an important role in shaping my view of a man. I grew up being dictated by how I should act and behave in public.” (Transcript A, Line 1-2)	Society and family are significant in perceiving manliness.
8	“Society and my family. Society has always been the basis for everyone on how each "man" should be portrayed. However, families would influence certain things that may or may not be perceived as manly by others.” (Transcript H, Line 1-2)	
9	“Family? You need to provide.” (Transcript I, Line 1)	Parents, specifically the father and other male family members, have influence in transmitting and reinforcing ideals about manliness.
6	“Of course, my parents are the ones who firstly explain how a man should act, which is from a Christian’s perspective. Since my father, who lives accordingly, shows how it should be done. It is not showmanship only; but instead it became how live his life, and that’s how I observed and followed his actions.” (Transcript F Line 1-3)	
5	“My father influenced my manliness. sheesh. He wants me to replicate the way he does things in his own accord.” (Transcript E, Line 1-2)	
2	“My parents, specifically my father, taught me on how to become a man by showing me examples.” (Transcript B, Line 1)	Oneself should have own sense of manliness and conform to social norms.
7	“As a kid, my role model was my eldest brother. He was rough but treated me arguably well. He made me do stuff on my own and taught me that I need to earn the good things in life with my own two hands.” (Transcript G, Line 1-3)	
10	“By myself, since I am a man myself so, I must influence myself to act like one, and I should and would act as one.” (Transcript J Line 1)	
3	“For me, being a man was not just about being physically strong. I wanted to be someone that my friends and family could count on and trust. I wanted to be someone that could take care of them when they needed it most. I wanted to be able to protect them. So the primary reason that influenced my manliness was my family and friends. The way it influenced me was by making me become a better person. It made me want to improve my relationships with my family and friends and become a better person.” (Transcript C, Line 1-5)	
4	“Successful peoples. It carved a memory to my brain that to be a successful person, you need to be strong and disciplined.” (Transcript 4, Line 1)	Inspirations are helpful to build strong and discipline.

Table 13. *Do you feel pressure to create a facade or image for other people to make you look manly? In your opinion, how does machismo culture influence your attitude toward seeking professional psychological help?*

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
3	“Men are often pressured to create a facade or image on other people for them to look manly. This can be done through their clothing, how they talk, how they act, and even how they walk. I think it is important to be yourself because you should not feel the pressure to conform to an image or facade for others. I’ve always been a little skeptical about seeing a professional psychologist. I’ve always had this feeling that I’m strong and can handle anything on my own, but deep down, I know that I need help. It’s not that I don’t trust myself, but I think that machismo culture has influenced my attitude towards seeking professional help. I don’t think it’s bad to want to take care of yourself, but I think that it is important to seek out professional help when you need it.” (Transcript 3, Line 1-5)	Machismo influenced the attitude toward professional psychological help, however, seeking help shouldn’t be anxious.
6	“I’d be lying if I said I don’t feel any pressure. Although majority of the society says a man should not be weak, it does not affect me wholly. Sometimes, showing weakness as a man is something to be proud.” (Transcript 6, Line 1-2)	Weaknesses do not alleviate the manhood of men, but acceptance of oneself needs and weak.
10	“Actually, no. why should I make a facade or image if they can actually see it physically? Though stereotypes are saying that man should be tough and shouldn’t be expressing or showing strong emotions, I myself is disagreeing with it. All people should express their own thoughts and emotions because it is in our rights to do so.” (Transcript J, Line 1-2)	
5	“I don’t feel any pressure creating a facade because the machismo culture that influences my attitude is more of an illusion. It is up for a man to decide if he wants to conform to this ideal. Furthermore, seeking professional psychological help does not mean it is unmanly; but rather, it is a separate case. Its either a man can be so masculine but with a psychological problem, or a man not so macho but mentally stable.” (Transcript E, Line 1-3)	Conform stereotype exists and affects the attitude but oneself will decide to adherence to it.

7	“No, it doesn’t really affect me. if I need help, I will seek it. but I still believe that limit testing is important, and I prefer to be a bit crazy and broken rather than spoiled and ignorant.” (Transcript G, Line 1)	
1	“When I was younger, it was a big deal to make a face that everyone will appreciate, but as I grew older, I realized that their perception of me does not really matter.” (Transcript A, Line 1)	
8	“No. For me, not much at all.” (Transcript H, Line 1)	
2	“I don't feel pressure by other people. I think if the environment is so toxic that they will judge you and base their respect for you through you manliness, that's what can influence me in seeking professional help.”	Pressure doesn’t prolong in seeking professional psychological help.
4	“Nope. Since I know that I am doing this to make me a better person. It's more of a personal choice rather than an influence of machismo culture”	
9	“No, I'm not actually aware of this machismo culture, and I don't give a shit”	Insufficient knowledge to machismo culture and attention.

Table 14. *Have you ever thought about seeking psychological help when you were having a hard time? What would be the reaction of the people near you or the society if they ever found out you were seeking professional mental help? As a man, how do you deal with mental disturbances when you see signs of needing professional help?*

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
10	“Well, in this case, I haven’t thought of looking for professional help since I am my own comfort and I also have my friends to vent out my feelings with. But as a man and often have mental disturbances like problems and other stuff, I personally recommend to at least say it to people whom you really trust and comfortable with. There are no signs that can actually be a mark to being able to know if we need to seek a professional for our mental difficulties.” (Transcript J, Line 1-3)	Resistance to acknowledging the psychological problems and alternative to freely expressing oneself through the social support
1	“I have not thought of seeking any professional help since I did not consider it to be detrimental to my mental health. I deal with any mental disturbance by talking to my friends and by talking to my mother.” (Transcript A, Line 1-2)	
5	“I never thought about seeking psychological help. If there will be a time I would seek professional help, I would probably think that others will see me as weak. The way I resolve my mental disturbances is by accepting the fact that there are things that I cannot control. I still think it is up to an individual to how he deals with such circumstances.” (Transcript E, Line 1-3)	
6	“Honestly, I have an introverted personality, which means I tend not to open myself to anyone. I think they would be surprised that I, who always show myself as active person, would actually seek mental help. Although I always tend to think what others think of me, if I desperately need help, it will not matter to me anymore and just disregard it.” (Transcript F, Line 1-3)	Society’s ideology toward men perceived as dominant and non-expressive individuals creates the perception of toughness.
3	“No, society and people around you would be very judgmental if they knew you were struggling with mental health. As a man, sometimes you may notice that you are not as mentally stable as you think you should be. It can be hard to talk to friends and family members about your feelings or even see a professional therapist. However, it is important to seek help when you need it, especially if it means avoiding other mental health issues such as depression. It is important for men to take care of themselves and their mental health because there are so many other things that we can do in our lives.” (Transcript C, Line 1-5)	
9	“I do not; I guess they’ll be bothered or worried? Men don’t seek professional help. Their relatives does it for them. I won’t volunteer myself. There is an analogy that a crazy person won’t be telling anyone that he’s crazy unless he’s faking it.” (Transcript I, Line -3)	
2	“As of now, I never thought of seeking professional help. I think in my environment, they will give me empathy on the reasons why I seek professional help. And when it comes to mental disturbance, I seek help first to my elders on any advice, and it always helps me.” (Transcript B, Line 1-3)	Resisting psychological help because of the orthodox expression of emotions that measure femininity and weakness regardless of the substantial emotional distress experienced.
8	“Not really. Generally not warm because of unorthodox practices. Personally, I open up to my loved ones.” (Transcript H, Line 1)	
7	“Yes, nothing much because I have good friends. The only people who would make fun of me for seeking help would be strangers that I don’t	Having social and emotional support that can show their vulnerabilities and mechanism in

- care about. If I ever feel lonely and depressed, I talk to my female friends and try to hang out with them. Being vulnerable to female friends feels nice. Male friends are fine too, but I don't do it as often." (Transcript G, Line 1-3)
- 4 "Nope. In today's world, it's easier to seek professional mental help since society accepts it. When I have mental disturbances, I unwind through meditating." (Transcript D, Line 1 -2)
- managing emotions.

Table 15. What proposal would you make to encourage more men to seek professional psychological help?

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
3	"As a man, it is difficult to open up to others. It is even harder to admit that you need help. There are many men who feel they are not good enough or they do not deserve help. What would you do if you were in a position where you could make an effort to encourage more men to seek professional psychological help? I would create a campaign that encourages men to seek professional psychological help. My campaign would be called "Man Up" and would encourage men to seek professional psychological help by showing them how much they can improve their lives and how much better they can feel once they get the help they need." (Transcript C, Line 1-3)	To overcome these barriers, respondents suggested intervention and encouraged more men to seek professional psychological help-seeking
10	"I am actually thinking of peer focus group discussion (FGD). Society actually left a mark for men that they should always be tough and brute, and they shouldn't be soft or feminine-moving, and should not show emotions, This is actually wrong, I am condoning this mindset and stereotype since all people are entitled to show their true feelings and emotions regardless if they are a man or a woman. In this FGD, men would be less likely to be shy and let out the things they are actually keeping inside their minds. FGDs are a good way to connect and communicate with people who are not necessarily have the same experiences with all other people in the group, but in a way, they can share their thoughts and emotions so that they would know that there are people who will always listen and understand their situations." (Transcript J, Line 1-5)	
8	"Be true to themselves. Society is transitioning to a more transparent one. Proposing a way to educate and raise awareness to people about psychological help as also being real medical help could be one." (Transcript H, Line 1)	Assessment of mental health state if need to seek further help.
5	"It is okay for men to seek professional psychological help, and seeking for it does not mean its unmanly. Protecting psychological health is the same as protecting your body." (Transcript E, Line 1-2)	
2	"My only advice is if you think you need professional psychological help, don't think about the others and think about yourself." (Transcript B, Line 1)	
6	"I think testimonies from men who overcame their mental difficulties because of professional help, could somehow motivate others to do it too." (Transcript F, Line 1)	Establishing accessible support systems and using testimonials and peer support.
9	"Be with the one who care for you the most. They can tell if you need one." (Transcript I, Line 1)	
1	"To be more open about how men really feel. Having a solid support system that is convenient and is accessible would help." (Transcript A, Line 1)	
7	"I propose that they stop listening to propaganda. Don't be sheeple and use their brains for a change. Extreme ideas exist so that we can find our own gray areas. Shutting down or following one extreme is irresponsible. Carefully think things through, because there is no going back. One skill that I mastered years ago was introspection, and I highly recommend learning it. Knowing oneself thoroughly feels rough, but it's better than joining the bandwagon of society." (Transcript G, Line 1-6)	Emerged unrealistic machismo ideologies which numerous of participants identified as significant barrier preventing men from seeking professional psychological help
4	"I don't know what to answer." (Transcript D, Line 1 -2)	

The present study examined the association between machismo and attitude toward seeking professional psychological help. Thus, considering the significant findings of the study, there are relevant limitations that affected the statistical analysis of the study. Particularly, in Tables 4 to 6, regarding the level of machismo when grouped according to demographic profile, the number of respondents according to civil status and employment status were not equally divided. The majority of the respondents are single (93%), married (6%), and separated, with only 1 respondent. Hence, the results show that there is no significant difference.

In contrast to a previous study with an equal number of respondents per demographic that the demographic profile of men has a significant correlation with the continuing development of machismo, indicates that as the males get older, the level of machismo increases and adherence to it, suggests that in shaping the help-seeking attitude, marriage has a significant influence on it as married

males are willing to express emotions. These findings underlie the study of Oliffe (2022) on how a man with intimate relationships has rendered masculinity adverse or adopted complete dominance and superiority. Furthermore, in the study of Thurnell-Read (2016), men are often trained to avoid discussions about masculinity that expand beyond toughness and other topics that are socially defined as male. Marriage and parenthood have been shown to trigger related views and changes in men's sense of selfhood.

The study also revealed that attitudes toward seeking psychological help vary across different demographic profiles. Considering single early adult males tend to have a negative attitude towards seeking psychological help than married and separated respondents. According to Horn et al. 2013, married men were revealed to have lower rates of mental illness due to the prior support of their spouse in seeking formal psychological help and moral support as partners. It shows a better psychological adjustment and is indicated as an apparent "marriage benefit" for married and also for separated males who experienced being married. This supports that never married or single males have trouble venting out their emotional or psychological concerns.

Additionally, employed and unemployed respondents also show a willingness to seek professional psychological help than self-employed respondents. A study by Bergman et al. (2020) found that a comparison between employed and self-employed have a minimal difference in seeking mental help. Investigated that self-employed respondents are less likely to experience depressive symptoms that parallel the reason why self-employed do not intend to seek psychological help. Respondents with employed employment status had the most depressive symptoms that made them more vulnerable and intended to seek psychological help. As well as those unemployed early adult males. Gaskell (2019) found that unemployment is significant factor in the depreciation of the mental health of males, as they have the role of being the provider. It is an obvious burden for males who are unemployed to be psychologically disturbed, which makes them more vulnerable and have a positive attitude toward seeking professional psychological help. Similarly, those employed in the private sector have a positive attitude towards seeking psychological help, as stated by Minot (2022), as private sector companies, firms, and employers foster mental health support and expose the employees to the importance of psychological help-seeking to result in a more open and positive attitude towards seeking mental help. However, the public sector shows an agreeable negative attitude towards seeking professional help based on the article by Eduardo (2022), which found that working in the public sector plays a big part in the good façade of the citizenry, law enforcement, positive attitude, and social service personnel, all of these responsibilities should be taken to account and take on an extra level of community responsibility. This results in an ideology that employees of public service should be emotionally reserved and, with greater responsibilities in the community, employed in the public sector, find no time for seeking psychological help and only be able to rely on themselves.

The present study revealed that with the interference of male family members and a cultured environment inside the home, gender roles or machismo qualities are developed, supported by Quintana (2021), that Hispanic males raise their children, and machismo is frequently maintained. There is only one proper way to be a male in Hispanic cultures. One must be diligent and knowledgeable about "manly" things. To support and protect the wife and children, males must use their skills. Never ask for assistance and must possess strength. Additionally, a previous study by Wahto and Swift (2016) revealed that several studies have endeavored to identify the variables that serve as barriers to obtaining psychological treatment in males. Data demonstrates that men, on average, have more negative views regarding psychological service encounters. Many men may be less inclined to seek psychiatric care for disorders like depression since conventional masculine standards push them to repress or deny difficulties. Specific signs of sadness may be disguised by other expression styles seen as more acceptable for males. In general, males are typically discouraged from getting treatment since the act of requesting aid might suggest a loss of status and autonomy, especially for men. Another factor that likely contributes to men's generally more negative views regarding obtaining professional psychological assistance is gender-role conflict. The adverse cognitive, emotional, and behavioral effects of acting in a way that deviates from stereotyped gender-role standards are known as gender-role conflict. Furthermore, it was revealed that males do not comply with the expected norms formed by society, such as being tough, providing for themselves, for family, or being emotionally reserved, but males tend to act this way not to display manliness but the ideal way to show their will and purpose as a man.

Conclusions

After a careful analysis of the gathered data from the respondents, the researchers were able to come up with the following conclusions.

Civil status, nature of employment, and employment status have no significant difference in terms of their level of machismo coherently; there is no specific area that will indicate an increase in the machismo level when grouped according to demographic profile. Additionally, qualitative findings revealed the level of machismo of the participants was built upon the patriarchal social system.

There is a significant difference in the level of attitudes towards seeking professional psychological help of respondents when grouped according to demographic profile. An early male adult's civil status may play a substantial role in their attitudes toward seeking help. Single men have the highest rating that tends to agree with the attitude scale among the three groups indicating that single respondents have a negative attitude and are less likely to seek psychological help compared to the other two groups, which are shown to be more open to the idea of seeking help. Overall, the findings of attitudes towards seeking professional psychological help when grouped according to demographic profile revealed that there is a significant difference between the two variables.

The overall attitude of the respondents toward seeking professional psychological help is negative, wherein the respondents were likely to agree with the statements from the survey that states negative attitudes toward seeking mental help.

There is a significant relationship between the two variables. The result is a strong positive correlation; therefore, there is a direct relationship between the variables that exist, wherein the increase in the level of machismo and the increase in negative attitude toward seeking professional psychological help.

Family dominance and social learning are important factors in developing men's attitudes, perceptions of gender, and understanding of what behaviors are proper for males.

Findings suggest machismo qualities such as being a provider, strong, and protector do not entirely for fulfilling the standard social norm towards men. It is revealed that men tend to act this way not to display manliness but as a way to show their will and purpose as a man.

As the last resource, some men have the tendency to seek professional psychological assistance if unable to manage stress and other psychological issues.

For the hypothesis, the researchers concluded that the result of One-way ANOVA for H01 falls under no significant difference between the level of machismo when grouped according to demographic profile, indicating failure to reject the null hypothesis. The decision for H02 revealed that there is a significant difference between the level of attitudes toward seeking professional psychological help when grouped according to demographic profile, indicates to reject the null hypothesis. Lastly, for the decision for H03, the result of the Pearson correlation coefficient falls under a strongly positive correlation; therefore, the study accepts the alternative hypothesis and rejects the null hypothesis.

The following recommendations are presented based on the findings and conclusion of the study:

Expand the study to include a broader range of age groups, particularly middle-aged and late adulthood, as well as those from dominant fields such as inspector officers, the military, or the air force, to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between machismo and help-seeking attitudes.

Consider socio-economic status and religion when examining the impact of machismo on help-seeking attitudes, as several participants in this study highlighted the influence of their religion in their responses to open-ended questions.

Future researchers may consider recruiting an equal distribution of participants across various relationship statuses, such as single, separated, widowed, or divorced. This would provide a fair distribution of data and a better understanding of the relationship between machismo culture and help-seeking attitudes across different relationship statuses.

Future researchers may explore the impact of family dynamics, such as the number of siblings, parents' civil status, and relationships with family members on machismo and help-seeking attitudes. This understanding can inform education and awareness campaigns to encourage families to promote formal help-seeking behaviors among early adult males.

Future researchers may instead opt to do a face-to-face or physical survey to increase the generalizability of the data and avoid biases in selecting respondents. With the study supplied an online survey, such respondents with email addresses are the only ones who can participate in the study. Furthermore, the use of different points of the Likert scale (e.g., 5-point) with a neutral option for the respondents.

Mental health professionals can utilize the study's results to improve the practice and assist early adult males in seeking formal help. This can be done by developing interventions and awareness campaigns that address the importance of psychological help-seeking.

These recommendations are presented with the aim of advancing a deeper understanding of the correlation between machismo and attitudes toward seeking professional psychological help. These recommendations also seek to stimulate the development of effective interventions that will encourage early adult males to seek professional psychological help when needed.

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